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The Growth of Involuntary Part Time in Italy

In Sardinia 17 workers out of 100 work involuntarily in part time

Istat calculates the percentage of workers who work in involuntary part-time. Involuntary part-time is defined by Istat as follows: "*Percentage of employees who declare they have a part-time job because they have not found a full-time job out of the total number of employees*".

Ranking of the regions by value of involuntary part-time in 2018. Sardinia is in first place by value of involuntary part-time in 2018 with a value of 16.80, followed by Calabria with an amount of 15.50 units and Sicily with an amount of 15.30. In the middle of the table there are Tuscany with an amount of 12.40 units, Umbria with a value of 12.10 units and Molise with a value of 11.40. Valle d'Aosta closes the ranking with an amount of involuntary part-time workers equal to 10.00, followed by Veneto with an amount equal to 9.60 units and Trentino Alto Adige with an amount equal to 7.30 units. On average in 2018 in the regions considered the value 12 workers out of 100 experienced involuntary part time.

Ranking of regions by value of involuntary part-time in the period 2004-2018. Sardinia is in first place for the value of the change in involuntary part-time workers with an amount equal to 9.90 equivalent to a value of 143.48%, followed by Abruzzo with an amount equal to 9.10 units equivalent to 227,50% and from Puglia with an amount equal to 9.00 units equivalent to 180%. Campania closes the ranking with a value of 6.30 units equal to a value of 91.30%, followed by Molise with a value of 6.00 units equal to an amount of 111.11% and Trentino Alto Adige with a value of amount equal to 5.40 units equal to 284.21%. On average in the period considered, the value of involuntary part-time increased by approximately 7.62 units, equal to an amount of 191.72%.

North. The value of involuntary part-time in the North increased between 2014 and 2018 from an amount equal to 10.10 to an amount equal to 10.30 units or a variation of 0.20 units equal to a percentage change of 1, 98%. Between 2014 and 2015 the value of involuntary part time in the North remained constant at a value of 10.10 and then decreased to 10.00 in 2016. Subsequently, the value of involuntary part time decreased from 10.00 to to 9.70 units or equal to an amount of -0.30 units equal to -3.00%. Between 2017 and 2018 the value of involuntary part time increased from an amount equal to 9.70 units up to an amount of 10.30 units or a variation equal to an amount of 0.60 units equal to a value of 6,19%.

Center. The amount of the involuntary part-time value in central Italy had a fluctuating trend in the period between 2014 and 2018. However, both in 2014 and in 2018 it had the same amount or equal to a value of 12.70. Between 2014 and 2015 the value of involuntary part-time in the center went from an amount equal to 12.70 units up to a value equal to 13.20 units or equal to a value of 0.50 units equal to an amount of 3.94%. In the transition between 2015 and 2016 the value of involuntary part-time in the Center decreased from an amount equal to 13.20 units up to a value equal to 13.00 or equal to a variation of -0.20 units equal to a amount of -1.52%. Between 2016 and 2017 the value of involuntary part-time decreased in the Center from a value of 13.00 to a value of 12.50 units or equal to a change of -0.50 units equivalent to -3, 85%. Between 2017 and 2018 the value of involuntary

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part-time increased from an amount equal to 12.50 units up to a value equal to 12.70 units or equal to a value of 0.20 units equivalent to 1.60%.

Southern Italy. Between 2014 and 2018 the value of involuntary part-time employees in the South went from an amount equal to 14.00 units up to a value equal to 14.30 units or equal to a variation of 0.30 units equivalent to a value of 2.14%. Between 2014 and 2015 the amount of involuntary part time went from an amount equal to 14.00 to a value equal to 14.10 units or equal to a change of 0.10 units equal to an amount of 0, 71%. In the transition between 2015 and 2016, the value of involuntary part-time increased from a value of 14.10 units to a value of 14.20 units or a variation equal to a value of 0.10 units equivalent to a amount of 0.71%. In the transition between 2016 and 2017 the value of the involuntary part-time decreased from an amount equal to 14.20 units up to an amount equal to 13.90 units or equal to a value of -0.30 units equivalent to a value of -2.11%. In the transition between 2017 and 2018, the value of involuntary part-time increased from an amount equal to 13.90 units up to a value equal to 14.30 units or equal to an amount of 0.40 units equal to 2.88 %.

Italy. The value of involuntary part-time personnel increased between 2014 and 2018 from an amount equal to 11.70 units up to a value of 11.90 units or a change equal to a value of 0.20 units equal to a value of 1.71%. Between 2014 and 2015 the value of involuntary part-time in Italy increased from an amount equal to 11.70 units up to a value equal to 11.80 units or equal to a value of 0.10 units equal to 0.85 %. Between 2015 and 2016 the value of involuntary part-time in Italy remained on average equal to 11.80. Between 2016 and 2017 it decreased from an amount equal to 11.80 units up to a value equal to 11.40 units or equal to a value of -0.40 units equal to a value of -3.39%. In the transition between 2017 and 2018, the value of involuntary part time increased from an amount equal to 11.40 units to a value of 11.90%.

Clusterization. A clustering with k-Means and t-SNE algorithm is proposed below to verify the presence of clusters capable of being traced back to the three Italian macro-regions. From the analysis, through the optimization of the Silhouette coefficient, the following clusters result:

- Cluster 1: made up of Sicily, Sardinia, Calabria, Lazio;
- Cluster 2: composed of Valle d'Aosta, Veneto, Friuli-Venezia Giulia, Emilia-Romagna, Trentino-Alto Adige, Lombardy;
- Cluster 3: made up of Molise, Liguria, Umbria, Basilicata, Abruzzo, Tuscany, Campania, Puglia, Piedmont, Marche.

As evident from the analysis with the k-Means algorithm we can underline the existence of a cluster, or cluster 2, which tends to represent the northern regions in an integrated way with the exception of Liguria and Piedmont. While cluster 1 and cluster 2 tend to have a heterogeneous representation of both southern and central regions. Therefore, even though there are 3 clusters, they do not adequately represent the distinctions between Central, Northern and Southern Italy.

Machine Learning and Predictions. The ANN-MLP algorithm or Artificial Neural Network with Multilayer Perceptron was used to predict the 2018 data compared to the 2004 data. The model was trained with 70% of the sample. The results show that the prediction of the data of the involuntary part-time of 2018 as a function of the data of the involuntary part-time of 2004 for the Italian regions makes a metric sense with the following values:

- $R^2 = 0.67$;
- Mean Absolute Error = 0.19;
- Mean Squared Error = 0.043;
- Root Mean Square Error = 0.208

- Mean Signed Difference = 0.023.
- The hyper-parameters used are as follows:
- maximum number of iterations = 100;
- number of hidden layers - deep learning = 1;
- number of hidden neurons per layer = 10.

That is, a low-depth neural network was used.

Multivariate panel data regression. The following model is then estimate:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{PartTimeInvolutario}_{it} &= \mathbf{a}_1 + \mathbf{b}_1(\mathbf{TassoDiOccupazione})_{it} \\
 &+ \mathbf{b}_2(\mathbf{TassoDiMancataPartecipazioneALLavoro})_{it} \\
 &+ \mathbf{b}_3(\mathbf{OccupatiSovraistruiti})_{it} \\
 &+ \mathbf{b}_4(\mathbf{TassoDiInfortuniMortaliEinabilit\`aPermanente})_{it} \\
 &+ \mathbf{b}_5(\mathbf{RedditoMedioDisponibileProCapite})_{it} \\
 &+ \mathbf{b}_6(\mathbf{GraveDeprivazioneMateriale})_{it} \\
 &+ \mathbf{b}_7(\mathbf{BassaIntensit\`aLavorativa})_{it}/
 \end{aligned}$$

The results show that involuntary part time is positively associated with the following variables:

- Employment rate;
- Rate of Non-Participation in Work;
- Over-educated employed;
- Severe Material Deprivation;
- Low Work Intensity.

Unintentional part time is negatively associated with the following variables:

- Accident rate and permanent disability;
- Average Available Income Per Capita.

The following considerations arise:

- Involuntary part-time work tends to represent a certain dynamism of the labor market as indicated by the positive relationship with the employment rate;
- Involuntary part time can also be due to the lack of relationship between the world of training and the labor market;
- Involuntary part time increases with the inefficiency of the labor market, the low activism of the working population and poverty.
- Involuntary part-time work decreases with per capita income growth, meaning that regions with greater production capacity for added value are also more likely to offer jobs that workers can accept with interest.

Conclusions. In summary, we can underline that about 12 out of 100 workers in Italy have accepted involuntary part-time work due to the lack of adequate offers on the part of the labor market. This percentage rises to 14 in the case of the South. However, as the analysis shows, it is mainly the southern and central regions that have a high number of involuntary part-time workers, a percentage that reaches up to 16.80% in the case of Sardinia. However, clustering shows the lack of a

classification that can fully represent the Italian macro regions with exceptions from the North that perform in a similar way from a metric point of view. The use of the Artificial Neural Network shows that a prediction of involuntary part time is also possible in the medium to long term. Finally, the regression panel data shows that involuntary part-time is certainly a manifestation of the inefficiency of the labor market and that it tends to decrease for regions with increasing added value.

Declarations

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Appendix

Ranking delle Regioni per part time involontario nel 2018.

Fonte: Istat-Best

Rank	Regione	Partime Involontario	Mean
1	<i>Sardegna</i>	★ 16,80	Over the mean
2	<i>Calabria</i>	★ 15,50	
3	<i>Sicilia</i>	★ 15,30	
4	<i>Puglia</i>	★ 14,00	
5	<i>Lazio</i>	★ 13,50	
6	<i>Liguria</i>	★ 13,50	
7	<i>Campania</i>	★ 13,20	
8	<i>Abruzzo</i>	★ 13,10	
9	<i>Basilicata</i>	★ 12,70	
10	<i>Toscana</i>	★ 12,40	
11	<i>Umbria</i>	★ 12,10	Under the mean
12	<i>Molise</i>	★ 11,40	
13	<i>Friuli-Venezia Giulia</i>	★ 11,20	
14	<i>Marche</i>	★ 11,00	
15	<i>Piemonte</i>	★ 11,00	
16	<i>Emilia-Romagna</i>	★ 10,60	
17	<i>Lombardia</i>	★ 10,00	
18	<i>Valle d'Aosta</i>	★ 10,00	
19	<i>Veneto</i>	★ 9,60	
20	<i>Trentino-Alto Adige</i>	★ 7,30	
	Media	12,21	

Crescita del Part-time Involontario tra il 2004 ed il 2018. Fonte: Istat-Bes.

Rank	Regione	%	Assoluto
1	<i>Sardegna</i>	143,48	9,90
2	<i>Abruzzo</i>	227,50	9,10
3	<i>Puglia</i>	180,00	9,00
4	<i>Liguria</i>	175,51	8,60
5	<i>Calabria</i>	118,31	8,40
6	<i>Toscana</i>	202,44	8,30
7	<i>Umbria</i>	218,42	8,30
8	<i>Friuli-Venezia Giulia</i>	239,39	7,90
9	<i>Valle d'Aosta/Vallée d'Aoste</i>	376,19	7,90
10	<i>Marche</i>	233,33	7,70
11	<i>Emilia-Romagna</i>	253,33	7,60
12	<i>Basilicata</i>	135,19	7,30
13	<i>Sicilia</i>	88,89	7,20
14	<i>Veneto</i>	284,00	7,10
15	<i>Lombardia</i>	212,50	6,80
16	<i>Piemonte</i>	161,90	6,80
17	<i>Lazio</i>	98,53	6,70
18	<i>Campania</i>	91,30	6,30
19	<i>Molise</i>	111,11	6,00
20	<i>Trentino-Alto Adige/Südtirol</i>	284,21	5,40
	<i>Media</i>	191,78	7,62

Part Time Involontario nelle Macro Regioni Italiane. Fonte: Istat-BES.

	V_2014	V_2015	V_2016	V_2017	V_2018	2014-2018
Nord	10,10	10,10	10,00	9,70	10,30	
<i>Variatione assoluta</i>		0,00	-0,10	-0,30	0,60	0,20
<i>Variatione percentuale</i>		0,00	-0,99	-3,00	6,19	1,98
Centro	12,70	13,20	13,00	12,50	12,70	
<i>Variatione assoluta</i>		0,50	-0,20	-0,50	0,20	0,00
<i>Variatione percentuale</i>		3,94	-1,52	-3,85	1,60	0,00
Mezzogiorno	14,00	14,10	14,20	13,90	14,30	
<i>Variatione assoluta</i>		0,10	0,10	-0,30	0,40	0,30
<i>Variatione percentuale</i>		0,71	0,71	-2,11	2,88	2,14
Italia	11,70	11,80	11,80	11,40	11,90	
<i>Variatione assoluta</i>		0,10	0,00	-0,40	0,50	0,20
<i>Variatione percentuale</i>		0,85	0,00	-3,39	4,39	1,71

Modello 7: Effetti fissi, usando 253 osservazioni
 Includi 20 unità cross section
 Lunghezza serie storiche: minimo 7, massimo 13
 Variabile dipendente: A39

	coefficiente	errore std.	rapporto t	p-value	
const	-27,6881	4,43837	-6,238	2,15e-09	***
A27	0,346025	0,0638448	5,420	1,53e-07	***
A28	0,689226	0,0435380	15,83	1,76e-038	***
A32	0,302337	0,0368329	8,208	1,71e-014	***
A33	-0,0842647	0,0336340	-2,505	0,0129	**
A42	-0,000223228	0,000120186	-1,857	0,0646	*
A45	0,0294245	0,0152190	1,933	0,0544	*
A48	0,0579729	0,0262705	2,207	0,0283	**

Media var. dipendente	8,726877	SQM var. dipendente	3,403276
Somma quadr. residui	107,4657	E.S. della regressione	0,689574
R-quadro LSDV	0,963181	R-quadro intra-gruppi	0,946793
LSDV F(26, 226)	227,3883	P-value(F)	1,0e-146
Log-verosimiglianza	-250,6799	Criterio di Akaike	555,3598
Criterio di Schwarz	650,7613	Hannan-Quinn	593,7430
rho	0,319855	Durbin-Watson	1,217488

Note: SQM = scarto quadratico medio; E.S. = errore standard

Test congiunto sui regressori -

Statistica test: $F(7, 226) = 574,51$

con p-value = $P(F(7, 226) > 574,51) = 4,01195e-140$

Test per la differenza delle intercette di gruppo -

Ipotesi nulla: i gruppi hanno un'intercetta comune

Statistica test: $F(19, 226) = 35,3878$

con p-value = $P(F(19, 226) > 35,3878) = 5,50771e-057$

Modello 8: Effetti casuali (GLS), usando 253 osservazioni
 Includere 20 unità cross section
 Lunghezza serie storiche: minimo 7, massimo 13
 Variabile dipendente: A39

	coefficiente	errore std.	z	p-value	
const	-42,0657	3,91105	-10,76	5,58e-027	***
A27	0,457077	0,0607945	7,518	5,55e-014	***
A28	0,704090	0,0441125	15,96	2,38e-057	***
A32	0,287051	0,0351952	8,156	3,46e-016	***
A33	-0,0581734	0,0311238	-1,869	0,0616	*
A42	0,000191305	0,000100663	1,900	0,0574	*
A45	0,0377991	0,0164287	2,301	0,0214	**
A48	0,0492489	0,0284047	1,734	0,0829	*

Media var. dipendente 8,726877 SQM var. dipendente 3,403276
 Somma quadr. residui 605,4920 E.S. della regressione 1,568869
 Log-verosimiglianza -469,3819 Criterio di Akaike 954,7638
 Criterio di Schwarz 983,0309 Hannan-Quinn 966,1366
 rho 0,319855 Durbin-Watson 1,217488

Note: SQM = scarto quadratico medio; E.S. = errore standard

Varianza 'between' = 0,97985
 Varianza 'within' = 0,475512
 theta medio = 0,80668
 corr(y, yhat)^2 = 0,824951

Test congiunto sui regressori -
 Statistica test asintotica: Chi-quadro(7) = 3302,57
 con p-value = 0

Test Breusch-Pagan -
 Ipotesi nulla: varianza dell'errore specifico all'unità = 0
 Statistica test asintotica: Chi-quadro(1) = 542,541
 con p-value = 5,27885e-120

Test di Hausman -
 Ipotesi nulla: le stime GLS sono consistenti
 Statistica test asintotica: Chi-quadro(7) = 63,8913
 con p-value = 2,51104e-011

Rank	N	Denominazione
b_1	A27	Tasso di occupazione (20-64 anni)
b_2	A28	Tasso di mancata partecipazione al lavoro
b_3	A32	Occupati sovra-istruiti
b_4	A33	Tasso di infortuni mortali e inabilità permanente
b_5	A42	Reddito medio disponibile pro capite
b_6	A45	Grave deprivazione materiale
b_7	A48	Bassa intensità lavorativa

PartTimeInvolotario_{it}

$$\begin{aligned} &= a_1 + b_1(\text{TassoDiOccupazione})_{it} \\ &+ b_2(\text{TassoDiMancataPartecipazioneAllavoro})_{it} \\ &+ b_3(\text{OccupatiSovraistruiti})_{it} \\ &+ b_4(\text{TassoDiInfortuniMortaliEInabilitàPermanente})_{it} \\ &+ b_5(\text{RedditoMedioDisponibileProCapite})_{it} \\ &+ b_6(\text{GraveDeprivazioneMateriale})_{it} \\ &+ b_7(\text{BassaIntensitàLavorativa})_{it} \end{aligned}$$

Rank	N	Denominazione
<i>b₁</i>	A27	<i>Tasso di occupazione (20-64 anni)</i>
<i>b₂</i>	A28	<i>Tasso di mancata partecipazione al lavoro</i>
<i>b₃</i>	A32	<i>Occupati sovra-istruiti</i>
<i>b₄</i>	A33	<i>Tasso di infortuni mortali e inabilità permanente</i>
<i>b₅</i>	A42	<i>Reddito medio disponibile pro capite</i>
<i>b₆</i>	A45	<i>Grave deprivazione materiale</i>
<i>b₇</i>	A48	<i>Bassa intensità lavorativa</i>